

APPENDIX 1 - INTERVIEW SCRIPT WITH COMPANY MANAGERS

- **Explain the thesis main goal:** *Propose and evaluate an approach for capturing, storing, discovering and visualizing SDP execution provenance data to support process analysis and data-driven decision-making.*

- **Explain the interview goal:** analyze some *questions* (and *goals*) that the approach tries to answer, using the provided process execution data.

Company and Manager Characterization Questions

Company 1 Company 2 Company 3

1. Job Title:
 2. Experience as a manager (in years): (0 – 1 – 2 – 3...8 – 9 – 10 - More than 10)
 3. Company Age:
 - 9 years or less operating
 - 10 year or more operating
 4. Company Size:
 - Micro: less 10 employees
 - Small: among 10 and 49 employees
 - Medium-size: among 50 and 99 employees
 - Large: more than 100 employees
 5. Brief description of the software development process(es) that you manage:

 6. What tool(s) do you use to analyze and make decisions about the process?
-

Opinion Questions

1. Considering the question “**CQ1 - What are the process activities, artifacts, resources, procedures, stakeholders, and the relations among them during the process execution?**”, the iSPuP approach gives the following views:

- Show to the participant the tool screen that displays these data (graph and table) and comment the following analysis: **CQ1 - Analysis:** It is possible to identify all the process elements that participated in process executions and the relation among them.

a. Is this analysis correct? () Yes () No () Partially

b. Can this analysis assist in the following decision-making?

CQ1 - Decision-Making Possibility: After identifying the process elements and the relation between them it is possible to find gaps (elements without association or inadequate relation established) in the analyzed data and try to correct it in next process executions.

() Yes () No () Partially

c. Could you answer **CQ1** using your current process management tool or dashboard? () Yes () No () Partially

d. What is the relevance of answering **CQ1** to support in analysis and decision-making processes?

() Extremely relevant

() Very relevant

() Somewhat relevant

() Not very relevant

() Irrelevant

2. Considering the question “**CQ2 - Which procedures are used by the process during its execution?**”, the iSPuP approach gives the following views:

- Show to the participant the tool screen that displays these data (graph and table) and comment the following analysis: **CQ2 - Analysis:** It is possible to check which procedures influenced an artifact development; Verify the procedures most useful in the analyzed instance(s), when a procedure is used by artifacts in a number greater than the average; Check procedures useless, i.e., although existing, these procedures were never used during the execution of the processes carried out by the organization.

a. Is this analysis correct? () Yes () No () Partially

b. Can this analysis assist in the following decision-making?

CQ2 - Decision-Making Possibility: When verifying that procedures influenced an artifact development, the process manager can evaluate if this fact was really planned/expected (in process modeling phase) or not; if this information is not specified in the process model, the process manager may include it; Being aware that a procedure is widely used by the process instances, the manager can better plan any changes in this procedure, since this can have a great impact on future executions; If a procedure has not been used during process execution, this information may be valid for the process manager to evaluate whether this procedure needs to be changed/reshaped to be used as planned or if it should be removed from the process. Another point of analysis would be the impact of not having a standard for the development of some artifacts – it could impact the quality level of generated artifacts, as well as cause errors by the difficulty of understanding some information in these artifacts, etc.

() Yes () No () Partially

c. Could you answer **CQ2** using your current process management tool or dashboard? () Yes () No () Partially

d. What is the relevance of answering **CQ2** to support in analysis and decision-making processes?

() Extremely relevant

() Very relevant

() Somewhat relevant

() Not very relevant

() Irrelevant

3. Considering the question “**CQ3 - Which activities had a high complexity (considering the number of associated stakeholders, artifacts, procedures and / or resources)?**”, the iSPuP approach gives the following views:

- Show to the participant the tool screen that displays these data (graph and table) and comment the following analysis: **CQ3 - Analysis:** It is possible to check when activities are associated with many stakeholders, artifacts, procedures and / or

resources, when compared to the other activities of the process, indicating that this activity could be more complex than others.

- a. Is this analysis correct? () Yes () No () Partially
- b. Can this analysis assist in the following decision-making?

CQ3 - Decision-Making Possibility: With the information provided by the analysis presented above, the process manager can evaluate if this fact was really planned/expected (in process modeling phase) or not; if this information is not specified in the process model, the process manager may change the process model to better represent the process that was in fact executed; A possible evaluation of the activities detected as more complex can be performed, aiming to divide it into less complex sub activities.

() Yes () No () Partially

- c. Could you answer **CQ3** using your current process management tool or dashboard? () Yes () No () Partially
- d. What is the relevance of answering **CQ3** to support in analysis and decision-making processes?
 - () Extremely relevant
 - () Very relevant
 - () Somewhat relevant
 - () Not very relevant
 - () Irrelevant

4. Considering the question “**CQ4 - Which activities had a high dependency (on other activities)?**”, the iSPuP approach gives the following views:

- Show to the participant the tool screen that displays these data (graph and table) and comment the following analysis: **CQ4 - Analysis:** It is possible to analyze the dependency between two activities, i.e., when occurred the exchange of some artifact by two activities, one activity using some entity generated or changed by the other. It is also possible to discover which activity occurred before or after another during execution time and to identify possible bottlenecks based on activities dependency.

- a. Is this analysis correct? () Yes () No () Partially
- b. Can this analysis assist in the following decision-making?

CQ4 - Decision-Making Possibility: From the previous analyzes, the process manager can confront the activities (and its flow) specified in the process model and how they occurred during execution. If there are any discrepancies, he can make changes in the process model, according to what he verified that, in fact, was executed. Another decision is trying to make changes in the process model in order to avoid bottlenecks, if it were identified in the previous analysis.

Yes No Partially

- c. Could you answer **CQ4** using your current process management tool or dashboard? Yes No Partially
- d. What is the relevance of answering **CQ4** to support in analysis and decision-making processes?
- Extremely relevant
 - Very relevant
 - Somewhat relevant
 - Not very relevant
 - Irrelevant

5. Considering the question “**CQ5 - What is the activities distribution among stakeholders?**”, the iSPuP approach gives the following views:

- Show to the participant the tool screen that displays these data (graph and table) and comment the following analysis: **CQ5 - Analysis:** It is possible to discover, from a stakeholder, all the activities (and the total of these activities) in which he/she participated, allowing to understand the activities distribution among stakeholders in the process execution.

- a. Is this analysis correct? Yes No Partially
- b. Can this analysis assist in the following decision-making?

CQ5 - Decision-Making Possibility: When verifying that a stakeholder is participating in much activities than others, the process manager can evaluate if this fact was really planned/expected (considering, for example, that a stakeholder was associated to a high number of activities because him/her always is attributed to activities with a lower level of complexity) or if it has been occurring due to an inadequate activity distribution during the process instantiation.

Yes No Partially

c. Could you answer **CQ5** using your current process management tool or dashboard? Yes No Partially

d. What is the relevance of answering **CQ5** to support in analysis and decision-making processes?

Extremely relevant

Very relevant

Somewhat relevant

Not very relevant

Irrelevant

6. Considering the question “**CQ6 - Which artifacts are known by a stakeholder, considering that in some process execution he/she created or modified such artifact?**”, the iSPuP approach gives the following views:

- Show to the participant the tool screen that displays these data (graph and table) and comment the following analysis: **CQ6 - Analysis:** It is possible to discover all the artifacts that were created and / or modified by a stakeholder, allowing to understand about what artifacts this stakeholder has some knowledge, considering he/she manipulated this artifact in some process execution. Considering the artifact view point, it is possible to discover all the stakeholders that have some knowledge about it, considering it was created or modified by them.

a. Is this analysis correct? Yes No Partially

b. Can this analysis assist in the following decision-making?

CQ6 - Decision-Making Possibility: in a future instantiation of the analyzed process, if a certain task is associated with a specific artifact, the process manager (or the responsible for the process instantiation) can allocate to this task a stakeholder with greater or less knowledge about the artifact to be manipulated during this task execution, according to the project objectives / goals.

Yes No Partially

c. Could you answer **CQ6** using your current process management tool or dashboard? Yes No Partially

d. What is the relevance of answering **CQ6** to support in analysis and decision-making processes?

- Extremely relevant
- Very relevant
- Somewhat relevant
- Not very relevant
- Irrelevant

7. Considering the question “**CQ7 - Which stakeholders are out of the average of created and/or modified artifacts?**”, the iSPuP approach gives the following views:

- Show to the participant the tool screen that displays these data (graph and table) and comment the following analysis: **CQ7 - Analysis:** It is possible to discover, from a stakeholder, the total and which artifacts were created or modified by him/her, allowing to understand the performance of this stakeholder considering the manipulation of process artifacts (e.g., if he/she usually creates new artifacts or if he/she only modifies them).

- a. Is this analysis correct? Yes No Partially
- b. Can this analysis assist in the following decision-making?

CQ7 - Decision-Making Possibility: When verifying that a stakeholder is creating more artifacts than others, the process manager can evaluate if they really need to be created or if there is a stakeholder’s lack of knowledge about the existing and available artifacts to be changed/adapted; - The process manager can better specify the responsible for the artifacts manipulation in a future instantiation of the analyzed process in order to obtain a better balance in relation to the stakeholder performance, considering the number of artifacts handled by the stakeholders.

Yes No Partially

- c. Could you answer **CQ7** using your current process management tool or dashboard? Yes No Partially
- d. What is the relevance of answering **CQ7** to support in analysis and decision-making processes?
 - Extremely relevant
 - Very relevant
 - Somewhat relevant
 - Not very relevant

Irrelevant

8. Considering the question “**CQ8 - What are the relationships among stakeholders?**”, the iSPuP approach gives the following views:

- Show to the participant the tool screen that displays these data (graph and table) and comment the following analysis: **CQ8 - Analysis:** It is possible to know the responsibility between the stakeholders during a process instance execution, detecting whether one stakeholder is responsible for many others or not.

a. Is this analysis correct? Yes No Partially

b. Can this analysis assist in the following decision-making?

CQ8 - Decision-Making Possibility: after analyzing the responsibility among stakeholders in executed instances, the process manager can use this information when allocating the responsibilities between stakeholders when a new instance of this process is created, according to the project objectives / goals.

Yes No Partially

c. Could you answer **CQ8** using your current process management tool or dashboard? Yes No Partially

d. What is the relevance of answering **CQ8** to support in analysis and decision-making processes?

Extremely relevant

Very relevant

Somewhat relevant

Not very relevant

Irrelevant

9. Considering the question “**CQ9 - Which roles each stakeholder assumes?**”, the iSPuP approach gives the following views:

- Show to the participant the tool screen that displays these data (graph and table) and comment the following analysis: **CQ9 - Analysis:** It is possible to analyze all the roles that have already been played by a specific stakeholder as well as, from a role, to verify which stakeholders can accomplish it.

a. Is this analysis correct? Yes No Partially

b. Can this analysis assist in the following decision-making?

CQ9 - Decision-Making Possibility: In a next instantiation of this process, if the process manager needs to allocate some person stakeholder in a specific activity that needs some pre-defined role, he can evaluate who can perform this role, based on stakeholders' skills. On the other hand, he can also decide who should participate in a training programming to be able to accomplish more roles during process execution.

Yes No Partially

- c. Could you answer **CQ9** using your current process management tool or dashboard? Yes No Partially
- d. What is the relevance of answering **CQ9** to support in analysis and decision-making processes?
- Extremely relevant
 - Very relevant
 - Somewhat relevant
 - Not very relevant
 - Irrelevant

10. Considering the question “**CQ10 - Which artifacts are derivations from others?**”, the iSPuP approach gives the following views:

- Show to the participant the tool screen that displays these data (graph and table) and comment the following analysis: **CQ10 - Analysis:** It is possible to discover all the artifacts derived from others in addition to verify the artifacts that were most used for the derivation of others and, therefore, are of great importance in the analyzed SDP.

- a. Is this analysis correct? Yes No Partially
- b. Can this analysis assist in the following decision-making?

CQ10 - Decision-Making Possibility: When verifying that an artifact was much used for the derivation of others, the changes in this artifact must be well planned to avoid that all the various other artifacts derived from it also need to be changed.

Yes No Partially

- c. Could you answer **CQ10** using your current process management tool or dashboard? Yes No Partially

- d. What is the relevance of answering **CQ10** to support in analysis and decision-making processes?
- Extremely relevant
 - Very relevant
 - Somewhat relevant
 - Not very relevant
 - Irrelevant

11. Considering the question “**CQ11 - Which artifacts or procedures are revisions from others?**”, the iSPuP approach gives the following views:

- Show to the participant the tool screen that displays these data (graph and table) and comment the following analysis: **CQ11 - Analysis:** It is possible to discover all the artifacts revisions, in addition to its latest versions / revisions.

- a. Is this analysis correct? Yes No Partially
- b. Can this analysis assist in the following decision-making?

CQ11 - Decision-Making Possibility: It is possible to evaluate when the last revision of a given artifact occurred, in addition to show if an artifact has already suffered many or no changes. This information can help in defining which artifact (or procedure) can / should be used in a next process execution.

Yes No Partially

- c. Could you answer **CQ7** using your current process management tool or dashboard? Yes No Partially
- d. What is the relevance of answering **CQ7** to support in analysis and decision-making processes?
- Extremely relevant
 - Very relevant
 - Somewhat relevant
 - Not very relevant
 - Irrelevant

Final Questions

1. Are the questions adequate and sufficient to achieve their goals?

() Yes () No () Partially

Justification:

Goal 1: Process structure identification during execution and possibilities for process redesign

- CQ1 What are the process activities, artifacts, resources, procedures, stakeholders, and the relations among them during the process execution?
- CQ2: Which procedures are used by the process during its execution?
- CQ3: Which activities had a high complexity (considering the number of associated stakeholders, artifacts, procedures and / or resources)?
- CQ4: Which activities had a high dependency?

Goal 2: Understanding stakeholder's involvement in process execution

- CQ5: What is the activities distribution among stakeholders?
- CQ6: Which artifacts are known by a stakeholder, considering that in some process execution he/she created or modified such artifact?
- CQ7: Which stakeholders are out of the average of created and/or modified artifacts?
- CQ8: What are the relationships among stakeholders?
- CQ9: Which roles each stakeholder assumes?

Goal 3: Tracking derivations and revisions among artifacts or procedures

- CQ10: Which artifacts are derivations from others?
- CQ11: Which artifacts or procedures are revisions from others?

2. Do you suggest any other question that should be considered relevant to assist in SDP analysis and decision-making?

3. Do you have any comment about the interview?

4. Do you have any comment about the approach?